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Antiplasticisation of Aryl Ether Epoxyes

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Air Travel and Pollution

Air Travel = most climate damaging form of transportation

4.6B people flying in 2019

Weight of plane = more fuel consumption = ADD cost to flying and environmental impact

SOLUTION: Light weight and high strength epoxy-fiber Composite = fuel saving

Composite

Carbon fiber

Very rigid and strong

Emission of green house gases = climate change

Polymer matrix

So much weaker!

Property mismatch

Failure of composites in the matrix

Toughening of Epoxy Resins

Fibre/matrix debonding

Matrix Fracture

Methodology

Synthesis of epoxy building blocks

Analysis of molecular structure

1:0.9 epoxy-hardener formulation

Nc1ccc(S(=O)(=O)c2ccc(N)cc2)cc1 44DDS
Nc1ccc(Oc2ccc(O)cc2)cc1 133APB
CN1C=CN1 EMI

Melting, mixing and degassing

Casting in silicone moulds

Epoxy-Amine curing (180C)

Results

Di- and tetrafunctional was successfully synthesized

The epoxies cured were cured different amine hardeners

Homogenous network with high Tg were developed

Polym. temp. and Tg of cured resins

Tough resins were developed: high modulus, strength and displacement to failure without significant reduction in Tg (antiplasticisation)

